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CAIRT Phase A Mission Performance and
Requirement Consolidation (PerReC)

Activity

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**CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for
case/impact studies for Consistent simulation of GW and
MLT
README-2**

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This manuscript describes the data used for demonstrating and assessing GW science in SciReC and PerReC as well as the generation of CAIRT orbit files from CLaMS simulations. In the second part it includes the simulated CAIRT L2 profiles of reactive nitrogen (NO_y) used as test dataset-product (TDS-P) in the CAIRT Phase A Performance and Requirement Consolidation study.</p>		
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.</p>		
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List of acronyms

ACT	ACross Track
ALT	ALong Track
AK	Averaging Kernel
CAIRT	Changing Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography explorer
MIAP	Mission Impact Assessment Plan
MLT	Mesosphere Lower Thermosphere
MO	Mission Objective of CAIRT
PerReC	CAIRT Performance and Requirement Consolidation study
SciReC	CAIRT Scientific and Requirement Consolidation study
SO	Scientific Objective of CAIRT
TDS-P	Test Data Set-Product
WP	Work Package (of PerReC if no other project mentioned)

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1 Part Gravity Wave

1.1 Introduction

A full cycle of demonstration for GW analysis contains the following elementary data:

1. data from a GCM or mesoscale model on a regular (usually lon-lat) grid
2. global scale wave coefficients
3. atmospheric data on CAIRT retrieval grid
4. L2b data from S3D GW analysis
5. zonal means, ...

Note that in this order we have assumed to infer the global scale wave parameters from the regularly gridded GCM data. In the final products we will need to perform a space-time estimate of wave coefficients, which are at yet not present.

Furthermore, the data of one step are not necessarily generated in one processing step / one program run. A subsequent number of steps may be carried out for one data format, in which case a larger amount of variables is contained in the subsequent 15 steps. We then list the variables as present after completing all steps in the flow.

1.2 Structure of the individual READMEs

Each README contains a short general text for explanation and a table which specifies all variable entries. This table is automatically generated from the meta-information contained in the NCDF files, utilizing, in particular, the long_name. In all JUWAVE related files we also follow the convention that coordinates are written in small caps and variables in capitals.

1.2.1 Some general naming rules

Part of the processing may generate the same variable but as a higher order processing step. One example is the scale separation which generates from a given variable such as temperature (TEMP) two new variables: the large-scale structures (BACKGROUND) and the small-scale variations (RESIDUAL). (How precisely the scale separation is performed is not stored in the variable description.) We here give some short descriptions with the individual files. When interpolating to the CAIRT data, the variable names and also long_name descriptions are inherited.

In order to make the files more self-explaining each file contains a history which documents (the) steps needed for generating this product.

1.2.2 Some general naming conventions

Table 1: Suffixes to names specifying later processing steps

Suffix	Explanation
BACKGROUND	Large scale structure of a given variable containing the zonal mean and the global scale waves up to a max. wave number
RESIDUAL	The full fields minus the background
SMOOTH	Calculation from the background field
RETRIEVED	Using an end-to-end simulation of forward radiance calculation and subsequent retrieval
MEAN	Is used in S3D files to indicate the average over a cube size. This is relevant for corrections accounting for a difference between average and centerpoint vertical wavenumber. It is introduced in the k-fit postprocessing. Can be combined with e.g. BACKGROUND
ALONG_WIND	For 2D quantities one can calculate the projection of the quantity to the wind direction. This is helpful to see whether GWs are roughly propagating opposite (the more usual case) or in the direction of the wind.

1.2.3 Table generation

The tables are automatically generated from the information contained in the NCDF files (e.g. long_name). Where this is not fully self-explaining additional notes will be provided. The program used is `ncdf_meta_to_latex_table.py` `ncdf_file.nc` which is part of the `juwave` package.

1.3 Atmospheric model data

1.3.1 ECMWF data

ECMWF data are sampled from the original spectral grid to a spatial regular lon-lat grid of 0.1° . This slightly reduces the spatial resolution for the 4.5km data, tests have shown, however, that the real information content of these very shortest scales is negligible.

We then interpolate in altitude from the hybrid model grid to a 500m equidistant geometric altitude grid and convert into 40 NCDF. The resulting files are described in Table 2.

Table 2: Typical format of a model field from ECMWF (here derived from the JUWAVE test file

detr_ecmwfr_ana_ml_14080112_km_atl lon_region55S45S_bgrTest_in.pt11.ref.nc

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
height	Geopotential Height	km	float32	height
lat	Latitude	degree_north	float32	lat
lon	Longitude	degree_east	float32	lon
time	Time	hours since 2014-0801T12:00:00	float64	time
N2	Square of the Brunt-Vaisala frequency from full temperature fields	1 / second ** 2	float32	time, height, lat, lon
N2_BACKGROUND	Background Square of the Brunt-Vaisala frequency from full temperature fields	1 / second ** 2	float32	time, height, lat, lon
N2_RESIDUAL	Residual Square of the Brunt-Vaisala frequency from full temperature fields	1 / second ** 2	float32	time, height, lat, lon
N2_SMOOTH	Square of the Brunt-Vaisala frequency from background temperature fields only	1 / second ** 2	float32	time, height, lat, lon
PRESS	Pressure	hPa	float32	time, height, lat, lon
PRESS_BACKGROUND	Background Pressure	hectopascal	float32	time, height, lat, lon
PRESS_RESIDUAL	Residual Pressure	hectopascal	float32	time, height, lat, lon
RICHARDSON	Richardson number	dimensionless	float32	time, height, lat, lon
SCORER	Scorer parameter after Durran, D. R. (2003)	1 / meter ** 2	float32	time, height, lat, lon
TEMP	Temperature	K	float32	time, height, lat, lon
TEMP_BACKGROUND	Background Temperature	kelvin	float32	time, height, lat, lon
TEMP_RESIDUAL	Residual Temperature	kelvin	float32	time, height, lat, lon

U	U component of wind	m s ⁻¹	float32	time, height, lat, lon
U_BACKGROUND	Background U component of wind	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
U_RESIDUAL	Residual U component of wind	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
V	V component of wind	m s ⁻¹	float32	time, height, lat, lon
V_BACKGROUND	Background V component of wind	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
V_RESIDUAL	Residual V component of wind	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
W	Vertical velocity	Pa s ⁻¹	float32	time, height, lat, lon

1.3.2 WACCM-X data

WACCM-X data is provided on a regular lon-lat grid with 0.25°, which corresponds to the simulation resolution. The data has been interpolated to a regular altitude grid of 500m spacing in the altitude range of 10 - 125km using a third order spline. The file structure is described in Table 3.

Table 3: Data structure of the interpolated WACCM-X model data.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
height	atmosphere altitude coordinate	km	float32	height
lat	latitude	degrees_north	float64	lat
lon	longitude	degrees_east	float64	lon
time	time	days since 2018-12-10 00:00:00	float64	time
N2_SMOOTH	Square of the Brunt-Vaisala frequency from background temperature fields only	1 / second ** 2	float32	time, height, lat, lon
PHIS	Surface geopotential	m2/s2	float32	time, lat, lon
PRESS	pressure	hPa	float32	time, height, lat, lon
PRESS_BACKGROUND	Background pressure	hectopascal	float32	time, height, lat, lon
PRESS_RESIDUAL	Residual pressure	hectopascal	float32	time, height, lat, lon
PS	Surface pressure	Pa	float32	time, lat, lon
T	Temperature	K	float32	time, height, lat, lon
T_BACKGROUND	Background Temperature	kelvin	float32	time, height, lat, lon
T_RESIDUAL	Residual Temperature	kelvin	float32	time, height, lat, lon
U	Zonal wind	m/s	float32	time, height, lat, lon
U_BACKGROUND	Background Zonal wind	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
U_RESIDUAL	Residual Zonal wind	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
V	Meridional wind	m/s	float32	time, height, lat, lon
V_BACKGROUND	Background Meridional wind	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
V_RESIDUAL	Residual Meridional wind	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
time_bnds	time interval endpoints		float64	time, nbnd
W	Vertical wind speed	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
W_BACKGROUND	Residual vertical wind speed	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon
W_RESIDUALS	Residual vertical wind speed	meter / second	float32	time, height, lat, lon

1.4 Global scale wave coefficients

1.4.1 For static regular fields (e.g. ECMWF, WACCM)

Table 4: Data description automatically generated from test case:

detr_ecmwfr_ana_ml_14080112_km_altlatlon_region55S45S_bgrTest_in_coefs.pt0.nc

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
height	Geopotential Height	kilometer	float32	height
lat	Latitude	degrees_north	float32	lat
lon	Longitude	degrees_east	float32	lon
time	Time	seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00	float32	time
zwn	Zonal wave number of planetary-scale waves	dimensionless	float32	zwn
COS_AMPL	cosine amplitudes of Temperature; normalized from real part of FFT result	kelvin	float32	height, lat, zwn
SIN_AMPL	sine amplitudes of Temperature; normalized from imaginary part of FFT result	kelvin	float32	height, lat, zwn

1.5 Atmospheric data on CAIRT retrieval grid

The data from the atmospheric model described in Sect. 3 are interpolated to the CAIRT retrieval grid. This includes the scale-separated fields, i.e. BACKGROUND and RESIDUAL fields. Temperatures are processed via an E2E simulation and RETRIEVED temperatures generated. No scale separation on these is performed as yet, but for S3D processing the interpolated BACKGROUND temperatures can be subtracted on the fly from TEMP_RETRIEVED.

Table 5: Data description automatically generated from atm_rg_noiseF2.1_2020-01-10_doy009.nc

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
altitude	altitude	km	float32	altitude
time	time	seconds since 2000-01-01	float64	time
track		dimensionless	float32	track
N2_SMOOTH	Square of the Brunt-Vaisala frequency from background temperature fields only	float32	1 / second	time, track, altitude
O3	Ozone mass mixing ratio	dimensionless	float32	time, track, altitude
PRESS	Pressure	hectopascal	float32	time, track, altitude
TEMP	Temperature	kelvin	float32	time, track, altitude
TEMP_BACKGROUND	air temperature background	kelvin	float32	time, track, altitude
TEMP_RESIDUAL	air temperature residual	kelvin	float32	time, track, altitude
TEMP_RETRIEVED	retrieved Temperature	kelvin	float32	time, track, altitude
U_BACKGROUND	eastward wind background	meter / second	float32	time, track, altitude
U_RESIDUAL	eastward wind residual	meter / second	float32	time, track, altitude

V_BACKGROUND	northward wind background	meter / second	float32	time, track, altitude
V_RESIDUAL	northward wind residual	meter / second	float32	time, track, altitude
W_RESIDUAL	upward wind residual	meter / second	float32	time, track, altitude
across_track_distance	distance in across-track direction	km	float32	track
along_track_distance	distance in along-track direction	km	float32	time
latitude	latitude	degree_north	float32	time, track, altitude
longitude	longitude	degree_east	float32	time, track, altitude

1.6 L2b data from S3D GW analysis

1.6.1 S3D on CAIRT

If you find problems please document them at: <https://jugit.fz-juelich.de/j.ungermann/juwave/-/issues/540>

Table 6: Data description automatically generated from s3d_refit_amplitude_TEMP_RETRIEVED_cs_5x7x5_kfit_TEMP_RETRIEVED_cs_11x9x11_nph8.0_npw0.8_at_m_rg_deadpix01_noiseF2.12_2020-01-08_doy007_bgr_sel_drag_rewritten.nc

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
altitude	altitude	kilometer	float32	altitude
time	time	seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00	float64	time
x_coordinate	projection_x_coordinate	kilometer	float32	x_coordinate
y_coordinate	projection_y_coordinate	kilometer	float32	y_coordinate
AMPL_RATIO	amplitude ratio between current fit and specified reference fit (e.g. re-fit and k-fit)	dimensionless	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
AMPL_SAT_RATIO	ratio between observed and saturation amplitude	dimensionless	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
CHI_SQUARE	chi square	dimensionless	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
COORD_ANGLE	azimuth of the local xy coordinate system, i.e., angle between the x-coordinate and the corresponding circle of latitude	degrees	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
CUBE_SIZE	size of the fitting cuboid (physical units)	meter	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate,

				wave_component, length_of_wave_vector
CUBE_SIZE_PTS	size of the fitting cuboid (pts)	dimensionless	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component, length_of_wave_vector
DIF_MEAN	average residuum in cuboid	kelvin	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
DRAG	drag as dF/dz from sum of all WC	m / s / day	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, length_of_gwmf_vector
DRAG_ALONG_WIND	drag in direction of wind	m / s / day	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
EASTNORTH_DRAG	drag from only eastward/northward waves	m / s / day	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, length_of_gwmf_vector
GWMF	pseudomomentum flux	Pa	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component, length_of_gwmf_vector
GWMF_ALONG_WIND	GWMF in direction of wind	Pa	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
K	wave vector; direction in local physical coordinates	1 / meter	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component, length_of_wave_vector
LATITUDE	latitude	degrees_north	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate

LONGITUDE	longitude	degrees_east	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
METHOD	method used for fit (list of choices: attribute flag_meanings)	dimensionless	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
NPTF	number of points used for fit	dimensionless	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
N_BACKGROUND	smoothed Brunt-Vaisala frequency in air	1 / second	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
N_BACKGROUND_MEAN	smoothed Brunt-Vaisala frequency in air, cube mean	1 / second	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
OMEGA_GB	ground-based frequency	1 / second	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
OMEGA_INTR	intrinsic frequency	1 / second	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
PHASE	wave phase wrt cuboid center	radian	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
PHASE_DIFFERENCE	phase difference between current fit and specified reference fit (e.g. re-fit and kfit)	radian	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
PRESSURE	air pressure	hPa	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
RELIABLE_FITS	Flag indicating reliability (True/1 for reliable)	dimensionless	int8	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
TOV	Total variance of original cuboid	dimensionless	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component

T_AMPLITUDE	temperature amplitude of fit	kelvin	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
T_BACKGROUND	smoothed air temperature	K	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
U_BACKGROUND	smoothed eastward wind	meter / second	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
U_BACKGROUND_MEAN	Smoothed eastward wind, cube mean	meter / second	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
VAL_MEAN	average value in cuboid; expected to be small after succesful scale separation	kelvin	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
V_BACKGROUND	smoothed northward wind	m/s	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate
V_BACKGROUND_MEAN	smoothed northward wind, cube mean	m/s	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, wave_component
WESTSOUTH_DRAG	drag from only westward/southward waves	m / s / day	float32	time, altitude, y_coordinate, x_coordinate, length_of_gwmf_vector

1.7 Zonal means and other higher-level (L3) data

The zonal mean GWMF and GW drag is stored in separate files containing the variables shown in Tab. 7.

Table 7: Data structure for the zonal mean GWMF and GW drag data. The GWMF is separated into eastward (northward) and westward (southward) direction for the zonal (meridional) GWMF component.

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
height	altitude	kilometer	float32	height
lat	latitude	de- grees_north	float32	lat
lon	longitude	de- grees_east	float32	lon
time	time	seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00	float32	time
ZONAL_MEAN_DENSITY	zonal mean air density	kg/(m**3)	float32	time, height, lat
ZONAL_MEAN_DRAG	zonal mean drag calculated from s3d_updown	m/s/day	float32	time, height, lat, length_of_gwmf_vector
ZONAL_MEAN_DRAG_EN	eastward / northward only zonal mean drag calculated from s3d_updown	m/s/day	float32	time, height, lat, length_of_gwmf_vector
ZONAL_MEAN_DRAG_WS	westward / southward only zonal mean drag calculated from s3d_updown	m/s/day	float32	time, height, lat, length_of_gwmf_vector
ZONAL_MEAN_GWMF	zonal mean directed momentum flux calculated from s3d_updown	pascal	float32	time, height, lat, wave_component, length_of_gwmf_vector
ZONAL_MEAN_GWMF_ALL_WC	zonal mean momentum flux calculated from s3d_updown after summing all WCs	pascal	float32	time, height, lat, length_of_gwmf_vector
ZONAL_MEAN_GWMF_EN	eastward / northward only zonal mean momentum flux calculated from s3d_updown	Pa	float32	time, height, lat, wave_component, length_of_gwmf_vector
ZONAL_MEAN_GWMF_EN_ALL_WC	eastward / northward only zonal mean momentum flux calculated from s3d_updown	Pa	float32	time, height, lat, length_of_gwmf_vector

ZONAL_MEAN_GWMF_WS	westward / southward only zonal mean momentum flux calculated from s3d_updown	Pa	float3 2	time, height, lat, wave_component, length_of_gwmf_vector
ZONAL_MEAN_GWMF_WS_ALL_WC	westward / southward only zonal mean momentum flux calculated from s3d_updown	Pa	float3 2	time, height, lat, length_of_gwmf_vector

1.8 CLAMS model data on synoptic grid

The original output from the Lagrangian CLaMS model is on an irregular grid which dynamically changes over time. This data has been interpolated on a regular 3D grid (pressure, latitude, longitude), with daily output frequency (12 UTC). In addition, certain meteorological fields (temperature, potential temperature, pressure) have been interpolated (linearly in latitude, longitude and logarithm of pressure) from ERA5 reanalysis data (native ECMWF model levels, $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ degree latitude \times longitude) onto the same grid. In the ICG = ICE cluster these data can be reached via:

`/usr/nfs/data/clams/icg198/cairt/clams_init_FV1/grid.`

Table 8: Data description automatically generated from `init_i3d_press_11010112.nc`

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
lat	Latitude	deg N	float32	lat
lon	Longitude	deg E	float32	lon
press	Pressure	hPa	float32	press
BA	Mean age from clock tracer mixing ratio which linearly increases in the lowest model layer (approximately the boundary layer)	year	float32	press, lat, lon
CH4	Methane volume mixing ratio	m^{**3} / m^{**3}	float32	press, lat, lon
F11	CFC-11 volume mixing ratio	m^{**3} / m^{**3}	float32	press, lat, lon
F12	CFC-12 volume mixing ratio	m^{**3} / m^{**3}	float32	press, lat, lon
F22	HCFC-22 volume mixing ratio	m^{**3} / m^{**3}	float32	press, lat, lon
GPH	Geopotential (divide by 9.81 m/s^{**2} to get geopotential height)	m^{**2}/s^{**2}	float32	press, lat, lon
N2O	N2O volume mixing ratio	m^{**3} / m^{**3}	float32	press, lat, lon
PRESS	Pressure	hPa	float32	press, lat, lon
SF6	Sulfur hexafluoride volume mixing ratio	m^{**3} / m^{**3}	float32	press, lat, lon
TEMP	Temperature	K	float32	press, lat, lon
THETA	Potential Temperature	K	float32	press, lat, lon

1.9 CLaMS: model data interpolated on CAIRT positions

The original CLaMS model output (irregular grid) has been interpolated to the CAIRT measurement positions using backward/forward trajectory mapping of CAIRT positions to the model output time and subsequent spatial interpolation (e.g. Ploeger et al., 2013). In addition, certain meteorological fields (temperature, pressure) have been interpolated (linearly in time, latitude, longitude and logarithm of pressure) from ERA5 reanalysis data (native ECMWF model levels, $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ degree latitude \times longitude) onto the same grid. In the ICG = ICE cluster these data can be reached via: `/usr/nfs/data/clams/icg198/cairt/clams_init_FV1_orbit/noonpos.`

Table 9: Data description automatically generated from CAIRT_RG_B1_clams_FV1_2011010112.nc

Name	Description	Units	Type	Dimensions
altitude	altitude	km	float32	altitude
time	time	days since 2000-01-01	float64	time
track		1	float64	track
BA	Mean age from clock tracer mixing ratio which linearly increases in the lowest model layer (approximately the boundary layer)	year	float32	time, track, altitude
CH4	Methane volume mixing ratio	m**3/m**3	float32	time, track, altitude
F11	CFC-11 volume mixing ratio	m**3/m**3	float32	time, track, altitude
F12	CFC-12 volume mixing ratio	m**3/m**3	float32	time, track, altitude
F22	HCFC-22 volume mixing ratio	m**3/m**3	float32	time, track, altitude
N2O	N2O volume mixing ratio	m**3/m**3	float32	time, track, altitude
PRESS	Pressure	hPa	float32	time, track, altitude
SF6	Sulfur hexafluoride volume mixing ratio	m**3/m**3	float32	time, track, altitude
TEMP	Temperature	K	float32	time, track, altitude
across_track_distance	distance in across-track direction	km	float32	track
along_track_distance	distance in along-track direction	km	float32	time
latitude	latitude	degree_north	float32	time, track, altitude
longitude	longitude	degree_east	float32	time, track, altitude

2 Part MLT

2.1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide a description of the test data set product (TDS-P) produced for the CAIRT impact study on the interplay of wave forcing, circulation and chemistry in the MLT in the frame of the CAIRT Performance and Requirement Consolidation study. Here, TDS-P are simulated CAIRT L2 NO_y profiles produced with the following steps:

1. WACCM-X high resolution model simulation in specified dynamics mode based on MERRA-2 meteorology
2. Re-gridding onto the CAIRT retrieval grid of model output for NO, NO₂, HNO₃, N₂O₅, CH₄, CO, and temperature, as well as cloud fraction
3. Simulation CAIRT L2 profiles with the Fast Level 2 Simulator (FL2S version 0.9.2, based on Linear Performance Estimation (LPE version 3) for threshold requirements.
4. Summation of NO, NO₂, HNO₃, and 2*N₂O₅ to NO_y for both model truth and FL2S output.
5. Computation of EPP-NO_y by means of tracer correlation of NO_y with CO and CH₄ following Funke et al., 2014)

These steps are defined in Sect. 2. A description of the TDS-P output files is provided in Section 3. References are given in Sect. 5.

2.2 Simulating CAIRT L2 profiles

2.2.1 WACCM-X simulations

The model truth of the MLT impact study uses specified-dynamics WACCM-X simulations. These simulations cover 10 December 2018 to 15 March 2019, a period characterised by enhanced dynamical variability in the winter hemisphere. To reproduce the meteorology of the 2018/2019 winter, the atmosphere at lower altitudes is nudged to MERRA-2 reanalysis data which confine both large-scale waves and gravity waves. Two simulations have been performed at NCAR:

- High-resolution simulation with 0.25 degree horizontal grid. A detailed description of the simulation setup can be found in Liu et al., 2024.
- Low-resolution simulation with 1 degree horizontal grid. A detailed description of the simulation setup can be found in (Solomon et al., 2019)

2.2.2 Re-gridding onto the CAIRT retrieval grid

The re-gridding of NR onto the CAIRT L2 retrieval grid is done based on the CAIRT orbit simulated in Phase 0 for one year and stored on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10262729>). Here, the CAIRT retrieval grid assumes a swath of 500 km with 25 km ACT sampling. This step has been performed already at NCAR in order to reduce the data volume to be transferred.

2.2.3 Perturbing the model truth using LPE and FL2S

The daily data interpolated onto the CAIRT retrieval grid are perturbed and smoothed according to CAIRT uncertainties from Linear Performance Estimation (LPE v3), done using FL2S (v 0.9.2 and described in the SWB ATBD, Höpfner et al., 2025). Simulating CAIRT L2 profiles with 100 km ACT sampling is done within the FL2S, applied only to the WACCM-X high-resolution output.

2.3 TDS-P file description

TDS-P files are formatted in netCDF, as described in Table 5 and 6 in of the ATBD about the scientific work bench (Höpfner et al., 2025). We restrict the FL2S output to the `vmr_noy_aknoisys` variable, that is, we only report the simulated CAIRT data with all perturbations (resolution degradation via AK application, noise errors, systematic errors). The model truth is stored in the variable `vmr_noy_ori`. A sample output for the high-resolution case and date 11 Dec 2018 is given below:

```
netcdf file:/Users/berndfunke/Downloads/SSW19_20181211_nmodall_noy.nc {
  dimensions:
    time = UNLIMITED;    // (11429 currently)
    altitude = 135;
    track = 4;
    corner = 4;
    bnds = 2;
  variables:
    double time(time=11429);
      _FillValue = NaN; // double
      :axis = "T";
      :standard_name = "time";
      :long_name = "time";
      :_CoordinateAxisType = "Time";
      :bounds = "time_bnds";
      :units = "days since 2000-01-01";
      :calendar = "standard";
      :_ChunkSizes = 512U; // uint

    float altitude(altitude=135);
      _FillValue = NaNf; // float
      :axis = "Z";
      :long_name = "altitude over WGS84";
      :standard_name = "altitude";
      :_CoordinateAxisType = "Height";
      :units = "km";
      :positive = "up";
      :_ChunkSizes = 135U; // uint

    float latitude(time=11429, track=4);
      _FillValue = NaNf; // float
      :axis = "Y";
      :standard_name = "latitude";
      :long_name = "latitude";
      :units = "degrees_north";
      :bounds = "lat_bnds";
      :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U; // uint

    float longitude(time=11429, track=4);
      _FillValue = NaNf; // float
      :axis = "X";
      :standard_name = "longitude";
      :long_name = "longitude";
      :units = "degrees_east";
      :bounds = "lon_bnds";
      :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U; // uint

    float lat_bnds(time=11429, track=4, corner=4);
      _FillValue = NaNf; // float
      :long_name = "corner latitudes";
      :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U, 4U; // uint
```

```

float lon_bnds(time=11429, track=4, corner=4);
  :_FillValue = NaNf; // float
  :long_name = "corner longitudes";
  :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U, 4U; // uint

double time_bnds(time=11429, bnds=2);
  :_FillValue = NaN; // double
  :long_name = "bounds of time bin";
  :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 2U; // uint

float cc(time=11429, track=4, altitude=135);
  :_FillValue = NaNf; // float
  :units = "1";
  :long_name = "Cloud cover";
  :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U, 135U; // uint

float pressure(time=11429, track=4, altitude=135);
  :_FillValue = NaNf; // float
  :units = "Pa";
  :long_name = "Atmospheric pressure";
  :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U, 135U; // uint

float temperature(time=11429, track=4, altitude=135);
  :_FillValue = NaNf; // float
  :units = "K";
  :long_name = "Temperature";
  :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U, 135U; // uint

float vmr_noy_aknoisys(time=11429, track=4, altitude=135);
  :_FillValue = NaNf; // float
  :long_name = "NOY";
  :units = "mol/mol";
  :standard_name = "mole_fraction_of_noy_expressed_as_nitrogen_in_air";
  :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U, 135U; // uint

float ak_diag(time=11429, track=4, altitude=135);
  :_FillValue = NaNf; // float
  :long_name = "averaging_kernel_diagonal_element";
  :units = "1";
  :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U, 135U; // uint

float vmr_noy_ori(time=11429, track=4, altitude=135);
  :_FillValue = NaNf; // float
  :units = "mol/mol";
  :long_name = "NOY";
  :standard_name = "mole_fraction_of_noy_expressed_as_nitrogen_in_air";
  :_ChunkSizes = 1U, 4U, 135U; // uint

// global attributes:
:init_random_seed = "0";
:last_random_number = 0.5373746944118308; // double
:random_seed_method = "auto";
:history = "On 21-Feb-2025 15:50:39 : ../fl2s_run.py -v
./config_2018121x.py\n";
:platform = "EE11";
:instrument = "CAIRT";
:fl2s_version = "0.9.2";
:retrieval = "f3.0";
:file_vrs = "04p";

```

```
:input_model_scenario =  
"/Work_2/CAIRT_SB/CEEPS/waccmx_geolocated_highres.v02/netcdf_files/waccmx_cairt_o  
bs_20181211_v02.nc";  
:lpe_file_no = "/Work_2/CAIRT/lpe_v3_ref/lpe_v3_NO_mrd_thres_ref_1.nc";  
:lpe_file_no2 = "/Work_2/CAIRT/lpe_v3_ref/lpe_v3_NO2_mrd_thres_ref_1.nc";  
:lpe_file_n2o5 = "/Work_2/CAIRT/lpe_v3_ref/lpe_v3_N2O5_mrd_thres_ref_1.nc";  
:lpe_file_clono2 = "/Work_2/CAIRT/lpe_v3_ref/lpe_v3_ClONO2_mrd_thres_ref_1.nc";  
:lpe_file_hno3 = "/Work_2/CAIRT/lpe_v3_ref/lpe_v3_HNO3_mrd_thres_ref_1.nc";  
}
```

2.4 Versions, traceability and reproducibility

The codes used to produce this TDS-P are on the FZJ CAIRT git repository at [jugit.fz-juelich.de:cairt-scirec](https://jugit.fz-juelich.de/cairt-scirec).

The FL2S config file is provided below:

```
para2ref = {  
  'no': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',  
  'ch4': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',  
  'temperature': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',  
  'no2': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',  
  'n2o5': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',  
  'clono2': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',  
  'hno3': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',  
  'co': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',  
}  
  
lpe_ncdir = "/Work_2/CAIRT/lpe_v3_ref/"  
  
CSSn = 'SSW19'  
  
mod_ncdir =  
"/Work_2/CAIRT_SB/CEEPS/waccmx_geolocated_highres.v02/netcdf_files/"  
apr_ncdir =  
"/Work_2/CAIRT_SB/CEEPS/waccmx_geolocated_highres.v02/apriori_T/"  
  
# define fl2s parameters  
sol_activity = 0 # solar activity index (within 0 for low activity and 1  
for high activity). The default is 0.  
n_cal = 56 # calibration period length (in terms of acquisitions). The  
default is 100.  
akd_threshold = 0.003 # averaging kernel threshold. The default is 0.003.  
ak_noise_sys = {  
  'ak':{'noi':False,'sys':False},  
  'aknoi':{'noi':True,'sys':False},  
  'aksys':{'noi':False,'sys':True},  
  'aknoisys':{'noi':True,'sys':True},  
}  
  
# define across-track bins for different across-track averaging lengths  
of the lpe  
# decision 400 km x-track-width (scirec meeting 15Mar2023)  
act_bin_ind = {  
  100:[[2,6],[6,10],[10,14],[14,18]],  
  300:[[2,14],[2,14],[6,18],[6,18]],  
}  
  
# random generator seed method
```

```

# - auto: fixed seed based on date and target name + `random_seed`
(below)
# - fixed: uses `random_seed` for all targets and dates
# - random (or anything else): no specific seed used, gives non-
reproducible results
random_seed_method = "auto"

# fixed random seed or extra "jitter" for "auto"
random_seed = 0

# for faster test set to positive number to calculate only nmod_use
samples along the tracks;
nmod_use = -1

css_config = {
  'SSW19': dict(
    cdate_l = [
      '20181211', '20181212', '20181213', '20181214', '20181215',
      '20181216', '20181217', '20181218', '20181219', '20181220',
      '20181221', '20181222', '20181223', '20181224', '20181225',
      '20181226', '20181227', '20181228', '20181229', '20181230',
'20181231'
      '20190101', '20190102', '20190103', '20190104', '20190105',
      '20190106', '20190107', '20190108', '20190109', '20190110',
      '20190111', '20190112', '20190113', '20190114', '20190115',
      '20190116', '20190117', '20190118', '20190119', '20190120',
      '20190121', '20190122', '20190123', '20190124', '20190125',
      '20190126', '20190127', '20190128', '20190129',
      '20190130', '20190131',
      '20190201', '20190202', '20190203', '20190204', '20190205',
      '20190206', '20190207', '20190208', '20190209', '20190210',
      '20190211', '20190212', '20190213', '20190214', '20190215',
      '20190216', '20190217', '20190218', '20190219', '20190220',
      '20190221', '20190222', '20190223', '20190224',
      '20190225', '20190226', '20190227', '20190228',
      '20190301', '20190302', '20190303', '20190304',
      '20190305', '20190306', '20190307', '20190308',
      '20190309', '20190310', '20190311', '20190312',
      '20190313', '20190314', '20190315',
    ],
    para_soll = ['ch4', 'co', 'clono2', 'hno3', 'n2o5', 'no', 'no2',
'temperature'],
    mod_ncbasefil = 'waccmx_cairt_obs_{cdate}_v02.nc',
    # external apriori file, should be on the same grid as
`mod_ncbasefil`
    apr_ncbasefil = 'waccmx_cairt_obs_{cdate}_v02_{para}.nc',
  ),
}

```

3 Literature

Funke, B., López-Puertas, M., Stiller, G.P., von Clarmann, T., 2014. Mesospheric and stratospheric NO_y produced by energetic particle precipitation during 2002-2012. *J Geophys Res* 119. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JD021404>

Höpfner, M., Funke, B., Errera, Q., Raspollini, P., Sinnhuber, B.-M., Ungermann, J., 2025. CAIRT linear SWB ATBD (No. DEL-04-01a-ATBD-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0).

Liu, H.-L., Lauritzen, P.H., Vitt, F., 2024. Impacts of Gravity Waves on the Thermospheric Circulation and Composition. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 51, e2023GL107453. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023GL107453>

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Ploeger, F., Günther, G., Konopka, P., Fueglistaler, S., Müller, R., Hoppe, C., Kunz, A., Spang, R., Grooß, J.-U., and Riese, M.: Horizontal water vapor transport in the lower stratosphere from subtropics to high latitudes during boreal summer, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 118, 8111–8127, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrd.50636>, 2013